

Project CHANGES – Spoke 4

D11 – Implementation of pilot studies – Type A – v1.0

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Spoke information

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5	Engineering	ENG	Member
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1. Introduction

Within the research lines of Spoke 4, one of our main goals is to experiment with the use of virtual (energy-efficient) technologies within defined and representative real-case scenarios. In particular, we aim to experiment with them using different museum and art collection templates to design specific case studies, deriving and applying best practices that can be further adapted and reused in institutions and contexts with similar characteristics. The six templates of museums and art collections identified are described as follows:

- Type A – high-density and innovative museum;
- Type B – natural history and scientific museum;
- Type C – widespread art gallery;
- Type D – sites museums with tangible and intangible heritage and landscapes, among those that have either low or no virtual and digital implementations with a particular focus in southern Italy;
- Type E – historical palaces, labelled as museums, among the most important in the Italian heritage context, including UNESCO sites;
- Type F – demo-ethnic-anthropological museums, including rural culture museums (with less than 20,000 visitors per year), anthropological museums and museums of art and popular traditions.

In this deliverable, we describe the outcomes of the work conducted with the cultural heritage institutions we have contacted that are compliant with Type A, with whom we have established collaborative research projects. In particular, we have identified a set of cultural institutions with which we have set up specific research projects to put into practice existing and ad-hoc tools developed to provide a system to be freely reusable in a similar context by other cultural institutions not necessarily involved in the project.

Some of these projects, referred to as “*core*” case studies, have been conducted in collaboration with companies that provide implementation efforts and institutions that offer domain-specific cultural knowledge and citizen engagement. The companies involved were selected through a public call for applications, supported by the project's funds (i.e., cascade calls). These “*core*” case studies have also been accompanied by additional *research case studies* aligned with the project templates and goals, which the partners of Spoke 4 have used to experiment with further adoptions of the aforementioned workflow, methodologies and tools within the project's period.

2. "Core" case studies

2.1. MEI: Immersive Egypt Project. Testing positive immersive virtual reality experiences to showcase the history and evolution of Egypt's historic and modern landscapes and their connection to the artifacts in the museum's collection

Outline clear goals and objectives

The story editing and delivery platform of the case study Museo Egizio Interattivo (MEI) assists curators in writing and delivering interactive stories that bring into play situations and values typical of ancient Egypt, as brought to light by the processes of study and research. The creation of a software that helps during the production of stories and the management of interactive storytelling experiences of the Egyptian Museum, including research and study processes related to it, and the study and research processes involving it. The story editor allows the domain experts to sketch and refine a multilinear story, where the audience can affect the choices of the characters and thus contribute to determine the final story outcome. The story definition, which abstracts from the details of story delivery, is subsequently translated into a playable object tailored to the assets and equipment available for a given venue. The set of activities allowed us to achieve a dual objective: on the one hand, the creation of digital environments and characters that are accurate from a historical and scientific point of view, on the other, the creation of an immersive and interactive experience capable of enhancing the heritage of the Egyptian Museum and offering the public an innovative approach to cultural enjoyment

Describe the initial situation

The initial situation was constituted by a rich collection of assets from the Museo Egizio, including a few candidate stories, however, the entire system had to be developed from scratch.

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

The complete pipeline of the system comprises three main components, following the specifications of the AI and Storytelling prototype provided by the partners of the spoke (Unito):

- An Annotation Editor that enables curators and domain experts to annotate digitized museum assets, thus facilitating their use and reuse in the production of the immersive experience. These annotated assets are automatically combined to produce media for reproduction in the immersive room (e.g., an immersive interactive VR scene managed by a game engine).
- A Story Editor that facilitates the creation of interactive narratives by curators. Through a user-friendly graphical interface that guides the domain expert through the creation of the interactive story, this component generates a fully defined story in terms of narrative elements and text. The LLM-based generation tool is integrated within this component to assist the domain experts in the expression of the story.
- A Stage Manager that transforms the output of the Story Editor into a playable story, coordinating assets, textual descriptions, and visitor feedback to enable interactive storytelling.

Figure 2.1.1. The tool pipeline.

Annotator

The Annotator tool is designed for managing and enriching cultural and documentary data. It is implemented as a dedicated application in Aton and it supports database loading and server-side editing through a patch mechanism built into the applications, as well as importing individual items from a cloud collection (tested so far with artifacts and places).

Each item can be modified and enriched via a dedicated form, with automatic synchronization of the updates. The tool also connects to controlled vocabularies, such as type or provenance, thanks to a routine that automatically extracts the relevant terms from JSON taxonomies. Finally, it provides cover generation, either server-side in JSON (base64) format or as a direct client-side download.

Figure 2.1.2. A screenshot of the annotator tool.

We develop specific taxonomies for the different fields in order to ensure consistency and semantic accuracy across the dataset. Each main category (Characters, Artifacts, and Places) uses its own reference taxonomies for key attributes, developed in conjunction with the staff of the Egyptian Museum (curators, collection managers and data managers) from the representation of the items in the museum catalog.

The dataset is indexed by entity, meaning a list of “semantic concepts” rather than assets. For example, an entry in the dataset can be the table xyz, which is associated with a set of semantic information and a list of assets. Each asset, in turn, has additional information associated with it.

The dataset consists of three maps indexed by ID and divided by main category: Characters, Artifacts, and Places. Depending on the main category, the fields to be filled differ, specifically:

- Character
 - Name (free text)
 - Catalog number (catalog number from the Egyptian Museum)
 - Type (reference taxonomy: character)

- List of Dating (reference taxonomy: period)
- Description (free text)
- Cover (path to the thumbnail)
- Artifact
 - Name (free text)
 - Catalog number (catalog number from the Egyptian Museum)
 - Type (reference taxonomy: artifact)
 - List of Materials (reference taxonomy: material)
 - Provenance/Area (reference taxonomy: area)
 - List of Dating (reference taxonomy: period)
 - Description (free text)
 - Cover (path to the thumbnail)
- Place
 - Name (free text)
 - Catalog number (catalog number from the Egyptian Museum)
 - Type (reference taxonomy: place)
 - Provenance/Area (reference taxonomy: area)
 - List of Dating (reference taxonomy: period)
 - Description (free text)
 - Cover (path to the thumbnail)

In addition to these fields, there is also a **models** field that defines a list of specific assets, each with its own fields (whose taxonomy is asset-specific).

Here is a mockup of the dataset:

```
{
  "personaggi": {
    "P001": {
      "nome": "Amenhotep III",
      "numero_cat": "numero_catalogo_ME",
      "tipo": "Faraone",
      "datazioni": [
        "XVIII Dinastia"
      ]
    }
  }
}
```



```
"descrizione": "Nono faraone della XVIII dinastia egizia, noto per il  
periodo di prosperità e sviluppo artistico",  
"cover": "/path/alla/cover.jpeg",  
"models": [  
  "/path/al/modello.glTF",  
  "/path/al/tileson.json"  
]  
},  
"P002": {  
  "nome": "Imhotep",  
  "numero_cat": "numero_catalogo_ME",  
  "tipo": "Visir",  
  "datazioni": [  
    "III Dinastia"  
  ],  
  "descrizione": "Visir del faraone Djoser, architetto, medico e scriba,  
progettista della piramide a gradoni di Saqqara",  
  "cover": "/path/alla/cover.jpeg",  
  "models": [  
    "/path/al/modello.glTF",  
    "/path/al/tileson.json"  
  ]  
}  
},  
"manufatti": {  
  "M001": {  
    "nome": "Sarcofago di Meritamon",  
    "numero_cat": "numero_catalogo_ME",  
    "tipo": "Sarcofago",  
    "materiali": [  
      "Ebano",  
      "Oro",  
      "Lapislazzuli"  
    ],  
    "provenienza": "Valle delle Regine",  
    "datazioni": [  
      "XIX Dinastia"  
    ],  
    "descrizione": "Sarcofago riccamente decorato appartenente a Meritamon,  
figlia di Ramses II",  
    "cover": "/path/alla/cover.jpeg",  
    "models": [  
      "/path/al/modello.glTF",  
      "/path/al/tileson.json"  
    ]  
  },  
  "M002": {  
    "nome": "Tavolozza dello Scriba Amenemhat",  
    "numero_cat": "numero_catalogo_ME",  
    "tipo": "Paletta da Scriba",  
    "materiali": [  
      "Ebano",  
      "Calcite"  
    ],  
    "provenienza": "Elefantina",  
    "datazioni": [  
      "XII Dinastia"  
    ],  
    "descrizione": "Tavolozza da scriba con incisioni ieratiche e cavità per  
pigmenti",  
    "cover": "/path/alla/cover.jpeg",  
    "models": [  
      "/path/al/modello.glTF",
```

```
        "/path/al/tiles.json"
    ]
  }
},
"luoghi": {
  "L001": {
    "nome": "Tempio di Hathor a Dendera",
    "numero_cat": "numero_catalogo_ME",
    "tipo": "Tempio",
    "provenienza": "Dendera",
    "datazioni": [
      "Epoca Tarda",
      "Periodo Tolemaico",
      "Epoca Romana"
    ],
    "descrizione": "Complesso templare dedicato alla dea Hathor, costruito e
      ampliato durante diverse epoche",
    "cover": "/path/alla/cover.jpeg",
    "models": [
      "/path/al/modello.gltf",
      "/path/al/tiles.json"
    ]
  },
  "L002": {
    "nome": "Mastaba di Kagemni",
    "numero_cat": "numero_catalogo_ME",
    "tipo": "Mastaba",
    "provenienza": "Saqqara",
    "datazioni": [
      "VI Dinastia"
    ],
    "descrizione": "Tomba del visir Kagemni, che servì sotto i faraoni Teti e
      Pepi I, famosa per i suoi rilievi e pitture funerarie",
    "cover": "/path/alla/cover.jpeg",
    "models": [
      "/path/al/modello.gltf",
      "/path/al/tiles.json"
    ]
  }
}
}
```

Story editor

Each story is organized as a multilinear structure of scenes, with certain scenes offering choices that visitors can select during the experience to affect the progression of the story.

The backbone of the story editor is INCURSO, which provides the representational component of the editing tool. This hybrid ontology formally integrates interactive storytelling elements taken from existing models (SPICE Narrative Ontology and DRAMMAR ontology) with museum artifacts cataloging, providing a shared vocabulary for both domains. INCURSO serves two critical functions: it establishes a standardized terminology for interactive narratives and annotated museum artifacts, while also enforcing the necessary constraints and requirements for story creation.

This approach is essential for our architecture, which prioritizes component decoupling and reusability. By merging museum cataloging elements with interactive narrative structures, INCURSO creates a comprehensive framework that also incorporates references to multimedia resources – a necessary feature as stories will ultimately be delivered through various digital media platforms.

Figure 2.1.3. The representation of a Scene in the INCURSO ontology.

When developing each scene, curators are only required to provide minimal defining information for each narrative element. An LLM can then be prompted to expand upon this foundation to generate complete, engaging narrative text. Through the story editor the curator can graphically create the story plot and describe the content of each scene according to the patterns defined in the ontology, following an editing model devised and tested in collaboration with museum professionals and media editors through the development of intermediate prototypes. .

It also allows interaction with a Catalog of Historical Elements and a Generative Artificial Intelligence system, capable of enriching concise texts with timely and historically accurate details extracted from the museum collections.

It is important to stress that the Story Editor has been designed and implemented with the objective of configurability and reusability in mind. For this reason, it includes a set of configuration files that enable the modification of its settings, for what

concerns both the settings of the editor (scene parameters, object types) and the type and settings of the LLMs embedded in the editor. In the following, the software implementation of the Story Editor is described and the use manual of the tool is provided.

Finally, to test the effectiveness of the Story Editor, writing workshops have been organized with museum professionals, software developers, UX experts and writers (see the example script in Appendix 1).

Figure 2.1.4. Overview of the Story Editor.

Figure 2.1.5. Edit a story in the story editor.

Stage manager

This component acquires the description of the story in the output format of the Story Editing Manager, informed on the INCURSO Ontology, and converts it in a playable story with control elements and contents tailored to the environment in which it will be displayed to the audience.

In the following, the creation of the digital assets is described, with a specific focus on the reuse of existing models of archaeological finds and locations.

Figure 2.1.6. Room previsualization.

Environment Modeling in Blender

During the project, a complex digital modeling and reconstruction process was developed, aimed at creating an immersive historical and museum-like experience. The initial phases involved the use of Blender, an open-source 3D graphics software widely used for modeling, texturing, and digital animation. Various environments were modeled using this tool, both from material provided directly by the Egyptian Museum - in a perspective of reuse - and from resources self-produced by the team. For example, vector reconstructions of the dwellings, photographs, and previously processed photogrammetry of the archaeological sites were used as a starting point for the construction of the environments.

Figure 2.1.7. An example of environment.

Integration of digitized finds

A significant portion of the spaces was populated using digitized artifacts from the Egyptian Museum. These were acquired through laser scanning and photogrammetry, which allowed for extremely accurate 3D models that were subsequently integrated into the virtual scenes.

Alongside this material, additional 3D assets were produced from archival photographs and other historical sources. Through comparison with reference images, it was possible to faithfully reconstruct objects and architecture that no longer exist. To optimize production time and costs, libraries of existing 3D assets were also used, carefully selecting elements consistent with the context and integrating them harmoniously with the original models.

Figure 2.1.8. An example of a virtual scene.

Figure 2.1.9. An example of an object rendered in 3D.

Finalization on Unreal Engine

The environments were finalized on Unreal Engine, a real-time 3D development platform widely used in video games and, increasingly, for cultural and museum
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applications. During this phase, we worked on realistic rendering of the scenes, implementing environmental simulations such as the presence of water in rivers, atmospheric variations in the sky, and dynamic lighting. Extensive research was conducted on material textures, drawing on both existing libraries and photographs taken during a site visit to Egypt, which were then processed to generate customized 3D materials consistent with the historical reconstructions.

Figure 2.1.10. An example of a rendering in Unreal Engine.

Character concept and development

At the same time, the character concept was developed, based on a careful analysis of historical sources and narrative settings. In constant dialogue with the museum curators, ethnic characteristics, age groups, hairstyles, and other distinctive features were defined to ensure maximum accuracy and historical respect. The characters were created directly in Unreal Engine using the native Metahuman editor, which allows for the creation of highly realistic human models, fully rigged and ready for animation.

Figure 2.1.11. An example of a character.

Clothes realization

For the clothing, we chose to use Marvelous Designer, a software specifically designed for digitally modeling fabrics and clothing. After consulting with the curators and, where possible, drawing on museum artifacts and photographic material, historically accurate costumes were created. Once completed, the garments were rigged in Blender and then imported into Unreal Engine, where they were integrated with the Metahuman characters.

Figure 2.112. An example of clothes represented in 3D.

Character animations and rigging

The animations were created by combining existing libraries with custom animations developed specifically for the characters, using Metahuman's native rig. This allowed for believable movements that were consistent with the narrative.

Figure 2.1.13. An example of the work done for animation of characters.

Storyboard and multi-screen direction

For each scene in the storyboard, animated sequences were produced in Unreal Engine using the Level Sequence function. The entire narrative development was designed to accommodate multiple screens, with three different cameras for each scene. This choice strengthened the immersive nature of the experience, following the principles of multi-screen storytelling. At interactive decision-making moments, the scenes were structured to orient the viewer, assigning a different option to each screen. To facilitate understanding and audience participation, visual attention was focused on key subjects, making the decision-making process more intuitive and ensuring active engagement.

Figure 2.1.14. An example of the multi-screen environment.

Cut Scenes in Motion Graphics 2D

To support the narrative in the virtual environment, 2D motion graphics cut scenes were inserted with the aim of illustrating historical and scientific aspects of life in ancient Egypt in a clear and accessible way. These sequences, conceived as moments of in-depth exploration within the narrative, allowed for the integration of archaeological data and historical information in an immediate and visually engaging form of communication. The choice of 2D motion graphics allowed for the clear and simple representation of complex concepts and scenarios, such as daily practices, production processes, or social contexts. The cut scenes were developed in close collaboration with the curators to ensure the historical accuracy of the content and consistency with the project's scientific framework, thus proving to be a fundamental tool for cultural mediation within the immersive experience.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

Our architecture prioritizes component decoupling and reusability. To optimize production time and costs, libraries of existing 3D assets were also used, carefully selecting elements consistent with the context and integrating them harmoniously with the original models. Particular attention was paid to the choice of fonts and colors to ensure the experience is accessible and at the same time consistent with its context.

Results and added value

The set of activities allowed us to achieve a dual objective: on the one hand, the creation of digital environments and characters that are accurate from a historical and scientific point of view, on the other, the creation of an immersive and interactive experience capable of enhancing the heritage of the Egyptian Museum and offering the public an innovative approach to cultural enjoyment.

Figure 2.115. Another example of the multi-screen environment.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

The creation of an immersive and interactive experience is capable of enhancing the heritage of the Egyptian Museum and offering the public an innovative approach to cultural enjoyment. The cut scenes were developed in close collaboration with the curators to ensure the historical accuracy of the content and consistency with the project's scientific framework.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Writing workshops have been organized with museum professionals, software developers, UX experts and writers. The taxonomies and datasets were developed in conjunction with the staff of the Egyptian Museum and the character concept was developed in constant dialogue with the museum curators.

Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)

Writing workshops have been organized with museum professionals, software developers, UX experts and writers. The user interface and its realization in the immersive room of the Egyptian Museum build on the observations and test sessions run with the audience at Gallerie d'Italia in Turin in 2023.

Explain the exchange of knowledge by the winning companies regarding how the chosen technologies work and how to use them

We develop specific taxonomies for the different fields in order to ensure consistency and semantic accuracy across the dataset, developed in conjunction with the staff of the Egyptian Museum. The character concept was developed in constant dialogue with the museum curators and the cut scenes were developed in close collaboration with the curators.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

The development of the final pipeline has been in continuity with the prototypes developed in the WP3. In particular the skeleton of the stories has been preserved, and further work has been done in order to identify suitable LLMs for the task of the description generation.

Detail the digitalisation processes

A significant portion of the spaces was populated using digitized artifacts from the Egyptian Museum. These were acquired through laser scanning and photogrammetry, which allowed for extremely accurate 3D models that were subsequently integrated into the virtual scenes. Alongside this material, additional 3D assets were produced from archival photographs and other historical sources, and vector reconstructions, photographs, and previously processed photogrammetry of the archaeological sites were used as a starting point for the construction of the environments. To optimize production time and costs, libraries of existing 3D assets were also used, carefully selecting elements consistent with the context and integrating them harmoniously with the original models.

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

To support the experience, a simple, clear, intuitive, and accessible user interface was developed. Given the multiple-choice nature of the narrative, particular attention was paid to the readability of the options displayed to visitors and their layout. The user interface includes template screens, including scene title, question, multiple choices,

choice made, choice disabled, and returns to position O. The screens feature a timer that indicates how much time visitors have to move to their chosen answer and the lower portion of the screens features an area dedicated to subtitles. The user interface and its realization in the immersive room of the Egyptian Museum build on the observations and test sessions run with the audience at Gallerie d'Italia in Turin in 2023. Particular attention was paid to the choice of fonts and colors to ensure the experience is accessible and at the same time consistent with its context.

Particular attention was paid to the choice of fonts and colors to ensure the experience is accessible and at the same time consistent with its context.

The fonts chosen, both sans serif, are ABC Diatype for the titles (the font used by the Egyptian Museum for its new logo and current communications) and Atkinson Hyperlegible for the body text and subtitles.

Figure 2.1.16. Font used in the project.

Regarding colors, the requirement was to ensure that they were visible and intelligible even to individuals with visual impairments. The choice therefore focused on colors that contrast strongly with the background and with each other, in order to distinguish the responses to which they are associated.

Figure 2.1.17. Colours used in the project.

Outline software programming design

The complete pipeline of the system comprises three main components: an Annotation Editor that enables curators and domain experts to annotate digitized museum assets, a Story Editor that facilitates the creation of interactive narratives by curators with an LLM-based generation tool integrated within this component, and a Stage Manager that transforms the output of the Story Editor into a playable story, coordinating assets, textual descriptions, and visitor feedback to enable interactive storytelling. The backbone of the story editor is INCURSO, which establishes a standardized terminology for interactive narratives and annotated museum artifacts, while also enforcing the necessary constraints and requirements for story creation. The code is structured into StoryElements and ReactFlow, with nodes for Scene, Choice, and Info, and classes including Story, StoryElement, UndoStack, Scene, Choice, and Info. Details on the Stage Manager are described in the previous sections.

Training on use and maintenance

The Stage Manager has been configured to ensure quick start-up of audio-video sessions, simplified source switching, event scheduling, ease of management and

maintenance, and on-demand recording and streaming. The control room's system will acquire multimedia content, schedule its broadcast, and manage the synchronization of visual and audio elements, and the audio signal will be synchronized from the control room and broadcast via the DANTE protocol throughout the room.

Describe opportunities and objectives

The set of activities allowed us to achieve a dual objective: the creation of digital environments and characters that are accurate from a historical and scientific point of view and the creation of an immersive and interactive experience capable of enhancing the heritage of the Egyptian Museum and offering the public an innovative approach to cultural enjoyment.

Familiarise staff with technology through training sessions and workshops on self-guided learning

Writing workshops have been organized with museum professionals, software developers, UX experts and writers.

Collect staff feedback

The user interface and its realization in the immersive room of the Egyptian Museum build on the observations and test sessions run with the audience at Gallerie d'Italia in Turin in 2023.

Describe the experimentation session

On September 26-27-29 2025, an implementation of the immersive room was opened to the public in a temporary space made available by Robin Studio. The discussions and questionnaire are still being analyzed, however early analysis show positive feedback from the demo users.

Evaluate with real users to track of the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions

The user interface and its realization in the immersive room of the Egyptian Museum build on the observations and test sessions run with the audience at Gallerie d'Italia in Turin in 2023.

Identify strengths and weaknesses (possibly using a SWOT analysis)

STRENGTHS: The creation of digital environments and characters that are accurate from a historical and scientific point of view and the creation of an immersive and interactive experience capable of enhancing the heritage of the Egyptian Museum. The architecture prioritizes component decoupling and reusability and the system

includes a Stage Manager that transforms the output of the Story Editor into a playable story.

OPPORTUNITIES: The same narrative content can be conveyed through different media and languages and the integration of digitized artifacts and historical sources allows for faithful reconstructions. The multi-screen storytelling and interactive decision-making moments ensure active engagement.

Explain how the proposed solutions can foster citizens participation, accessibility, and social inclusion

Particular attention was paid to the choice of fonts and colors to ensure the experience is accessible and at the same time consistent with its context. The multiple-choice nature of the narrative and the clear, intuitive interface support audience participation and active engagement.

Conclusions

The project demonstrated how digital tools, immersive technologies, and interactive storytelling can be effectively combined to enhance the cultural heritage of the Museo Egizio. By developing a complete pipeline that spans from the annotation of assets to the creation of interactive narratives and their transformation into playable experiences, the team succeeded in producing historically accurate digital environments, characters, and stories. The integration of Blender, Unreal Engine, Metahuman, Marvelous Designer, and motion graphics allowed for the realization of complex virtual reconstructions that merge scholarly rigor with audience engagement.

The user interface and UX design aimed at the clarity of the multiple-choice interaction model, while the use of fonts and colors aligned with museum standards ensured consistency with the institution's visual identity. The experimentation phase at Robin Studio further validated the approach, providing valuable insight into the effectiveness of audience tracking with sensors and the responsiveness of the stage manager system.

Overall, the project not only produced a functioning immersive storytelling prototype but also highlighted the potential of reusing museum data, digitized artifacts, and curated taxonomies to create dynamic cultural experiences. The results suggest that immersive rooms, when paired with flexible software architectures and user-centered design, can open new opportunities for participation, education, and social inclusion, while laying the groundwork for future research in automation, accessibility, and broader dissemination across different platforms.

Identify technological gaps

Some technological gaps emerged concerning the specific requirements and implementation of sensors to guide the interactive story in Unreal Engine, which demand precise calibration, positioning, and integration to ensure reliable audience tracking. Another gap lies in the mixing of assets from different sources, since 3D models created through photogrammetry, archival reconstructions, and external libraries often required complex harmonization to achieve consistency in scale, style, and quality.

Describe any unforeseen issues that arose during the implementation

The main setback during development has been the delays in constructing the Sala Immersiva at the Museo Egizio. However, we created a demo of the project in the Robin Studio spaces to assess the quality of the work.

Delineate further lines of research

Further lines of research include the automatization of animations by allowing large language models to choose the most appropriate sequences in a tool-like fashion, reducing manual intervention. Another important direction is enabling LLMs to play through the stories themselves in order to identify the most common paths likely to be chosen by users, thus supporting the development of narratives with more balanced branching. Finally, analyzing the answers provided by visitors during the interactive experience can offer valuable feedback to the museum, helping curators refine both the content and the engagement strategies. In addition, there is the possibility of implementing these interactive stories in other stages such as totems or websites, extending accessibility beyond the immersive room.

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